

Association of carotid intima-media thickness with incident carotid plaque: Pooled analysis of 19 prospective cohorts from the Proof-ATHERO consortium

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Background and Aims: The association between carotid intima-media thickness (cIMT) and development of first-ever atherosclerotic plaque at the carotid artery has not yet been characterised fully. To provide clarity, we undertook an individual-participant data meta-analysis of 19 prospective cohorts from the Proof-ATHERO consortium.

Methods: Prospective cohorts that assessed cIMT at the common carotid arteries and recorded incident carotid plaque at one or more follow-up surveys were eligible for the analysis. We excluded participants with prior cardiovascular disease or with pre-existing plaque at baseline. We calculated study-specific odds ratios for incident carotid plaque and combined them using random-effects meta-analysis.

Results: We analysed data on 20,143 individuals from 19 studies (mean age 56 years [SD 9]; 54% female; mean baseline cIMT 0.71 mm [SD 0.17]). Over a median follow-up of 5.8 years, 7,652 individuals developed carotid plaque. Baseline cIMT was approximately linearly associated with the odds of developing incident carotid plaque. The age-, sex-, and trial arm-adjusted odds ratio for carotid plaque per one SD higher baseline cIMT was 1.40 (95% CI: 1.31-1.51; I^2 : 65.4%). The corresponding odds ratio further adjusted for ethnicity, smoking, diabetes, body mass index, systolic blood pressure, low-density and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and lipid-lowering and antihypertensive medication was 1.34 (95% CI: 1.24-1.45; I^2 : 59.2%; 14 studies; 16,172 participants; 6,334 incident plaques). There was no evidence for effect modification across several clinically relevant subgroups.

Conclusions: Our large-scale epidemiological evaluation demonstrates that cIMT is approximately linearly associated with the odds of developing first-ever carotid plaque, independent of traditional cardiovascular risk factors.